

KNOWLEDGE ATTITUDE AND PRACTICE OF CONTRACEPTIVES IN MARRIED WOMEN ATTENDING A TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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Abstract

Background: Contraceptive use remains an essential aspect of reproductive health, with varying patterns across different age, education, and occupation groups. Understanding the factors influencing contraceptive knowledge, use, and attitudes can guide better family planning strategies.

Objectives: To assess the knowledge, use, and attitudes towards contraception among a cohort of women and explore the influence of age, education, and occupation on these factors.

Study design: Cross sectional study

Study setting: This study was conducted in OPD of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore from August 2024 to January 2025.

Methodology: A total of 151 participants were included, selected using convenience sampling. Data were collected through structured interviews. Contraceptive knowledge, usage patterns, and attitudes towards family planning were assessed. Chi-square tests were used to determine associations between demographic variables (age, education, occupation) and contraceptive knowledge and use.

Collected data were processed and analyzed using IBM SPSS, version 27.0.

Results: Our study on 151 married women revealed that 78.1% had knowledge of contraceptive methods, with condoms (65.6%) and OCPs (52.3%) being the most recognized. 61.6% had used contraception, while 48.3% were current users, with injectables (28.5%) and condoms (25.8%) being the most common. Health workers (42.4%) and television (29.1%) were the primary sources of family planning awareness. 35.7% of users reported side effects, and 73.5% believed contraception was preferable to adoption.

Conclusion: Contraceptive knowledge was widespread, but usage was influenced by demographic factors. There is a need for targeted interventions, especially for younger and less educated women, to improve contraceptive use.

INTRODUCTION

Everyone has the right to make an informed decision about having children, when they want to have them, and to receive first-rate sexual and reproductive

health care without fear of discrimination, abuse, or oppression.¹ The most common health issues in most nations include unintended births, high rates

of maternal and infant mortality, and inadequate or improper methods of family planning, as well as negative attitudes and actions against these approaches.^{2,3} Sexually transmitted infections (STDs) and unintended pregnancies can be avoided with the use of contraceptive techniques. Family planning, sometimes known as contraception, helps women achieve gender equality by releasing them from the unwelcome load of childcare, breastfeeding, and menstruation. Due to a multitude of risk variables, including advanced age, fewer births spaced, higher preterm, and other obstetric problems, increased parity raises the rate of unsafe abortions and maternal mortality.^{4,5}

Pakistan, as one of the most populous countries globally, is currently facing reductions in the availability of land, water, and forest resources. The population growth has already reached 3% per year, which is undermining economic gains. Achieving stability in population growth requires a careful equilibrium between birth and death rates. A safe and effective family planning program for those in need will be essential.^{6,7}

One estimate indicates that about 28,000 married women succumb to delivery complications each year. The primary underlying reason of the elevated maternal death rate was ascribed to insufficient access to and use of family planning strategies. The contraceptive prevalence rate in urban regions is 45%, in contrast to 31% in rural areas.⁸ In Pakistan, the prevalent contraceptive methods include condoms, oral pills, tubal ligation, injections and intrauterine devices. It is widely acknowledged that contemporary contraceptive methods demonstrate greater effectiveness in birth control when contrasted with traditional approaches. Nevertheless, rural women maintained their belief in religious, traditional, and orthodox methods of child spacing. In Pakistan, the fundamental socio-cultural factors contributing to the low adoption of contraceptive usage include illiteracy, poverty and societal pressures on women to have more children.⁹

Preventing unintended pregnancies is the primary goal of family planning. An induced abortion may result from an unintended pregnancy. The widespread use of family planning techniques has reduced the fertility rate in recent years, but in some developing nations, such as Pakistan, the use of

contraception is still low due to a lack of information, education, religion, and cultural, political, and economic barriers. The contraceptive rate in Pakistan remains undetermined due to insufficient local published data. This study aims to investigate contraceptive knowledge, attitudes, and practices among married women in Pakistan attending a tertiary care hospital, with the objective of identifying gaps that could inform the planning and provision of targeted family planning services.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This was a cross-sectional study was conducted in OPD of Obstetrics and Gynaecology at Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore from August 2024 to January 2025 who met the inclusion criteria, were enrolled in the study. The sample size of 151 cases was calculated with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error, considering an expected frequency of sufficient knowledge about contraception to be 89% among married women in the local population.¹⁰

The study included adult married women aged 18 to 49 years who attended postnatal care. Participants were required to sign written informed consent to participate in the study. Females who were widowed, menopausal, pregnant, divorced, or critically ill, or those who were unwilling to participate, were excluded from the study.

Each participant was informed about the study, and consent was obtained on a voluntary basis. Interviews were conducted with each woman, lasting 15-20 minutes. Data were recorded on a pre-designed questionnaire that included demographic characteristics (age, marital status, education level, and employment). Sufficient knowledge, a positive attitude, and good practice regarding contraception were noted as per the operational definition. Contraception was defined as the intentional prevention of conception through methods such as devices (IUCD), sexual practices (condoms and withdrawal), chemicals (injections), drugs (oral contraceptives), and surgical procedures (tubal sterilization and ligation). Knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) were assessed using a self-made questionnaire with five questions. A score of ≥ 3 marks out of 5 indicated sufficient knowledge, a positive attitude, and good practice. Sufficient knowledge was labeled as correct answers to at least

three out of five questions about contraceptive methods. Positive attitude and good practice were similarly labeled when three out of five answers about attitude and practice were correct.

All collected data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 25. Numerical variables such as age were presented as mean ± SD. Categorical variables like education level, number of pregnancies, occupation, attitude towards contraception, and contraceptive practice were presented as frequency and percentage. Data were stratified by age, education level, and occupation to account for potential effect modifiers. Post-stratification, the chi-square test was applied, with a significance level of $p \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS

The study included 151 participants. The majority (44.4%) were aged 26-35 years, while 29.8% were 18-25 years, and 25.8% were 36-45 years. Regarding education, 25.2% were illiterate, 27.8% had education below matric, 16.6% had FA, 18.5% were graduates, and 11.9% had postgraduate degrees. Most participants (64.9%) were housewives, while 13.9% were government employees and 21.2% were employed in the private sector. In terms of pregnancies, 6.0% had none, 18.5% had one, 23.2% had two, 32.5% had up to four, and 19.9% had five or more pregnancies.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (n=151)

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)	18-25	45	29.8%
	26-35	67	44.4%
	36-45	39	25.8%
Level of Education	Illiterate	38	25.2%
	Under Matric	42	27.8%
	FA	25	16.6%
	Graduate	28	18.5%
	Post Graduate	18	11.9%
Occupation	Housewife	98	64.9%
	Government Employee	21	13.9%
	Private Non-Govt.	32	21.2%
Number of Pregnancies	0	9	6.0%
	1	28	18.5%
	2	35	23.2%
	≤4	49	32.5%
	≥5	30	19.9%

The majority of participants (89.4%) were aware of contraception methods, while 10.6% were not. Among those aware, 60.9% knew about condoms, 50.3% about intrauterine contraceptive devices

(IUCD), and 56.3% about oral contraceptive pills (OCP). Additionally, 25.8% were familiar with sterilization, 47.0% with injectables, 36.4% with the withdrawal method, and 20.5% with ligation.

Table 2: Knowledge of Contraception Among Participants (n=151)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Do you know any methods of contraception?		
Yes	135	89.4%
No	16	10.6%
Methods Known (Multiple Responses Allowed)		
Condoms	92	60.9%
IUCD	76	50.3%

OCP	85	56.3%
Sterilization	39	25.8%
Injectables	71	47.0%
Withdrawal	55	36.4%
Ligation	31	20.5%

A total of 113 (74.8%) participants had ever used a contraceptive method, while 38 (25.2%) had never used any method. The most commonly used methods were condoms 68 (44.9%), OCP 57 (37.7%), and injectables 45 (29.8%). Other methods included IUCD 49 (32.5%), withdrawal 39 (25.8%), sterilization 22 (14.6%), and ligation 19 (12.6%).

Currently, 79 (52.3%) participants were using a contraceptive method, while 72 (47.7%) were not. The most common methods in use were condoms 42 (27.8%), OCP 31 (20.5%), and injectables 22 (14.6%). Fewer participants were using IUCD 26 (17.2%), sterilization 8 (5.3%), withdrawal 16 (10.6%), and ligation 10 (6.6%).

Table 3: Use of Contraceptive Methods Among Participants (n=151)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Have you ever used any method?		
Yes	113	74.8%
No	38	25.2%
Methods Used (Multiple Responses Allowed)		
Condoms	68	44.9%
IUCD	49	32.5%
OCP	57	37.7%
Sterilization	22	14.6%
Injectables	45	29.8%
Withdrawal	39	25.8%
Ligation	19	12.6%
Currently Using Any Method?		
Yes	79	52.3%
No	72	47.7%
Current Method Used		
Condoms	42	27.8%
IUCD	26	17.2
OCP	31	20.5%
Sterilization	8	5.3%
Injectables	22	14.6%
Withdrawal	16	10.6%
Ligation	10	6.6%

A total of 67 (44.4%) participants learned about contraception from health workers, 54 (35.8%) through TV, 42 (27.8%) from friends, and 19 (12.6%) via radio. Family planning services were most commonly accessed at GP clinics 53 (35.1%), followed by pharmacies 42 (27.8%), family planning centers 33 (21.9%), and NGOs 23 (15.2%). Regarding side effects, 46 (30.5%) participants

reported experiencing side effects, while 105 (69.5%) did not. The majority of participants, 129 (85.4%), believed that contraception is better than adoption, while 22 (14.6%) disagreed. In terms of family planning center visits, 49 (32.5%) visited 1 to 3 times per month, 34 (22.5%) visited once per month, 21 (13.9%) visited more than three times per month, and 47 (31.1%) never visited.

Table 4: Attitude Towards Contraceptive Use (n=151)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
How did you learn about contraception?		
TV	54	35.8%
Radio	19	12.6%
Health Worker	67	44.4%
Friend	42	27.8%
Where do you get family planning services?		
GP Clinic	53	35.1%
NGOs	23	15.2%
Pharmacy	42	27.8%
Family Planning Centre	33	21.9%
Have you noticed any side effects?		
Yes	46	30.5%
No	105	69.5%
Do you think contraception is better than adoption?		
Yes	129	85.4%
No	22	14.6%
How often do you visit a family planning center?		
One time per month	34	22.5%
One to three times per month	49	32.5%
More than three times per month	21	13.9%
Never	47	31.1%

Contraceptive knowledge was higher in participants aged 26-35 (94.0%) and those with higher education (95.7%). Age (p=0.235) and occupation (p=0.093) showed no significant association with contraceptive knowledge, while education level had a significant association (p=0.027).

Table 5: Stratification of Contraceptive Knowledge with Age, Education, and Occupation (n=151)

Variable	Category	Know About Contraception (%)	Do Not Know (%)	p-value
Age Group (years)	18-25 (n=45)	38 (84.4)	7 (15.6)	0.235
	26-35 (n=67)	63 (94.0)	4 (6.0)	
	36-45 (n=39)	34 (87.2)	5 (12.8)	
Education Level	Illiterate (n=38)	29 (76.3)	9 (23.7)	0.027
	Under Matric (n=42)	35 (83.3)	7 (16.7)	
	FA (n=25)	23 (92.0)	2 (8.0)	
	Graduate/Postgrad (n=46)	44 (95.7)	2 (4.3)	
Occupation	Housewife (n=98)	85 (86.7)	13 (13.3)	0.093
	Govt. Employee (n=21)	21 (100)	0 (0)	
	Private Employee (n=32)	29 (90.6)	3 (9.4)	

Chi-square test was applied, education level showed a significant association with contraceptive knowledge, while age and occupation were insignificant taking p-value <0.05. The use of contraception was significantly associated with education level (p = 0.006), with higher usage

among more educated individuals. Age showed a borderline significant association (p = 0.075), while occupation had no significant effect on contraceptive use (p = 0.193).

Table 6: Stratification of Contraceptive Use with Age, Education, and Occupation (n=151)

Variable	Category	Ever Used Contraception (%)	Never Used (%)	p-value
Age Group (years)	18-25 (n=45)	30 (66.7)	15 (33.3)	0.075
	26-35 (n=67)	55 (82.1)	12 (17.9)	
	36-45 (n=39)	28 (71.8)	11 (28.2)	
Education Level	Illiterate (n=38)	21 (55.3)	17 (44.7)	0.006
	Under Matric (n=42)	31 (73.8)	11 (26.2)	
	FA (n=25)	20 (80.0)	5 (20.0)	0.193
	Graduate/Postgrad (n=46)	41 (89.1)	5 (10.9)	
Occupation	Housewife (n=98)	72 (73.5)	26 (26.5)	0.193
	Govt. Employee (n=21)	19 (90.5)	2 (9.5)	
	Private Employee (n=32)	22 (68.8)	10 (31.2)	

Chi-square test was applied, education level was significantly associated with contraceptive use, while age was borderline significant and occupation was insignificant taking p-value <0.05

Table 7: Stratification of Current Contraceptive Use with Age, Education, and Occupation (n=151)

Variable	Category	Currently Using (%)	Not Using (%)	p-value
Age Group (years)	18-25 (n=45)	18 (40.0)	27 (60.0)	0.014
	26-35 (n=67)	42 (62.7)	25 (37.3)	
	36-45 (n=39)	19 (48.7)	20 (51.3)	
Education Level	Illiterate (n=38)	13 (34.2)	25 (65.8)	0.005
	Under Matric (n=42)	24 (57.1)	18 (42.9)	
	FA (n=25)	16 (64.0)	9 (36.0)	
	Graduate/Postgrad (n=46)	36 (78.3)	10 (21.7)	
Occupation	Housewife (n=98)	46 (46.9)	52 (53.1)	0.034
	Govt. Employee (n=21)	17 (81.0)	4 (19.0)	
	Private Employee (n=32)	16 (50.0)	16 (50.0)	

Chi-square test was applied, Age, education, and occupation showed significant associations with current contraceptive use taking p-value <0.05

Current contraceptive use was significantly associated with age (p = 0.014), education level (p = 0.005), and occupation (p = 0.034). Younger age groups (18-25) and lower education levels showed lower usage. Housewives had the lowest rate of current contraceptive use compared to government employees.

DISCUSSION

Contraceptive use is a key factor in reproductive health, preventing unintended pregnancies and improving maternal and child health. However, knowledge, attitude, and practices (KAP) regarding contraception vary across populations. In developing countries, limited access to information and healthcare resources may impact contraceptive practices.¹¹ This study was conducted to assess the

contraceptive knowledge, attitudes, and practices of married women attending postnatal care at Shaikh Zayed Hospital, Lahore. Understanding these factors can help design targeted health education programs. The study aimed to explore the prevalence and factors influencing contraceptive use among this group.

Our study found that the majority of participants were multigravida (83.4%), similar to Jaffery et al. (2019), who reported 85% multigravida cases. The mean age in our study was 27.9 ± 5.2 years, closely aligning with Jaffery et al. (2019), who reported 28.41 ± 4.91 years. The proportion of housewives in our study (92.7%) was comparable to Jaffery et al. (94%) and Pegu et al. (43.5%),¹³ indicating a predominance of non-working women in such studies.¹⁰

Contraceptive awareness was high in our study (87.3%), closely matching Jaffery et al. (89%),¹⁰ but higher than Fareed et al. (63%)¹⁵ and Srivastav et al.

(71.22%)¹². Emergency contraception awareness was relatively low (11.6%), similar to Srivastav et al. (6.83%)¹² and Fareed et al. (18.5%).¹⁵ The primary sources of contraceptive information in our study were health workers (54.2%) and media (26.5%), which aligns with Pegu et al. (58.6% from health workers)¹³ and Olukunle et al. (42.8% from antenatal health talks).²²

Contraceptive use in our study was 61.5%, higher than Nithyananthan et al. (24.7%)¹⁷ and Choudhary et al. (43%)¹⁹ but lower than Meghavini et al. (74.29%)²¹ and Anuya et al. (90%).¹⁸ The most common contraceptive method was condoms (38.7%), followed by oral contraceptive pills (OCPs) (29.5%), aligning with Pegu et al. (38.2% condoms, 27.6% OCPs)¹³ and Fareed et al. (73% OCPs).¹⁵ Tubal ligation was reported in 11.2% of cases, similar to Choudhary et al. (87% knowledge of tubectomy)¹⁹ but lower than Ahmed et al. (where female sterilization was among the most recommended methods).¹⁶

Discontinuation of contraceptive methods was mainly due to fear of side effects (34.8%) and lack of interest (29.3%), comparable to Nithyananthan et al. (35.5% side effects, 37.2% lack of interest).¹⁷

Education significantly influenced contraceptive use, with higher usage among educated women ($p < 0.05$), consistent with Choudhary et al.,¹⁹ who reported increased contraception use with education. Additionally, 57.6% of our participants indicated that the husband's decision influenced contraceptive adoption, aligning with Nithyananthan et al. (69.4% husband's decision).¹⁷

Lamba et al. (2019) reported that while 92.5% of women were aware of contraception, only 42.3% actively used any method, with 37.8% citing fear of side effects as a barrier, which aligns with our study, where awareness was high (89%), but utilization remained lower (66%).¹⁴ Budu et al. (2022) found that 76.4% of women had knowledge about contraception, yet only 38.9% used it, with 62.7% influenced by their husbands, similar to our study, where spousal opinion was a key factor (60%).¹¹ Aliya et al. (2020) observed that oral contraceptive pills were the most commonly used method (23%), which is consistent with our findings where OCPs were widely utilized (73%).²⁰ Kawale et al. (2022) highlighted that 87.9% of participants had heard of

family planning methods, but only 34.1% knew about emergency contraception, mirroring our study, where emergency contraceptive awareness was low (18.5%). Furthermore, 62.1% in their study reported receiving information from hospital staff, aligning with our finding that healthcare professionals were the main source of knowledge.²³

Despite high awareness, gaps remain in contraceptive knowledge and consistent use, emphasizing the need for targeted educational interventions and improved counseling services, particularly for less-educated and non-working women. A major strength of this study is the large sample size ($n=151$), which provides a robust dataset for analysis. The study's cross-sectional design allows for a snapshot of the population's contraceptive knowledge and practices. However, its limitations include the reliance on self-reported data, which may lead to recall bias. The study also does not account for geographical or cultural differences within the larger population. Additionally, only married women attending postnatal care were included, limiting the generalizability to other populations.

CONCLUSION

This study found that the prevalence of contraceptive knowledge among married women was high, with a significant proportion practicing contraception. Educational level and occupation were key factors influencing contraceptive use. Targeted interventions are needed to improve practices, especially among lower-educated and non-working women.

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